

Academic Community's Attitudes and Perceptions on the Decision of Visiting Nature-Based Tourism Destinations in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Visits to nature-based tourism destinations can be influenced by many factors. External stimulus factors in the form of promotional material can influence decisions in conducting tourist visits. This study aims to analyze the attitudes and perceptions of the academic community relating to the decision to visit nature-based tourism destinations at the stage of induced demand based on tourism promotion materials in the form of printed and audio-visual materials. The study approach was carried out by distributing questionnaires to 270 academic community respondents divided into three categories, namely, lecturers, ecotourism students and communication students who answered questions in a closed ended form with a Likert scale 1-7 that assessed printed material and audio-visual promotion of nature-based tourism. The analytical method used is the Kruskal Wallis Test and the further Dunn Test. The results of the empirical study showed differences in assessment regarding the attitudes and perceptions of the academic community on tourism promotion material in influencing the decision to visit nature-based tourism destinations. Factors that influence the decision to make actual visits to nature-based tourism destinations are demographic characteristics, personal factors, external and psychographic factors in the academic community.

Keywords: Nature-based Tourism, Academic community, Promotional material, Attitude, Perception

INTRODUCTION

Tourism has a multiplier impact on various fields of development. Various types of tours are packaged attractively so that prospective tourists can visit tourist destinations. Including natural tourist destinations become one of the choices of tourists to visit in order to enjoy the beauty and uniqueness of natural and environmental resources. Nature-based tourism is explained as a trip to natural areas (Laarman & Durst (1987), Avenzora (2008), Lucas *et al* (1990) and Mehmetoglu (2007)). Mehmetoglu (2007) called it nature-based

tourism as a tourist or traveling to a relatively undisturbed area or an uncontaminated natural area with the aim of learning, admiring and enjoying the scenery. According to Lucas *et al* (1990) nature-based tourism is tourism that is based on enjoying natural areas and observing nature which usually has a low environmental impact, is labor intensive and is socially and economically feasible. Laarman & Durst (1987) emphasize the aspects of education, recreation and adventure and Boo (1990) in Avenzora (2008) defines tourism as natural areas.

The level of visits to natural tourist destinations is inseparable from the role of marketing through promotion. Promotion through print and audio-visual media is a choice of promotional forms used by the Ministry of Tourism to inform nature-based tourism destinations. Promotion can influence consumer purchasing decisions and as an effort to convey information (Sambathan & Good 2014; Hasan 2015; Baldemoro 2013; Mill & Morrison 2009). This promotional activity is carried out by using media that can communicate messages to the target audience. Print media as a guide / reference for potential or actual tourists in tourist destinations that have not been supported by information technology facilities. The form of printed material can be in the form of booklets, leaflets, tourism maps, brochures and others, while audio visual media in the form of VCDs that contain films about nature-based tourism destinations. The existing problems have not been measured by tourist attitudes and perceptions of printed and audio-visual promotional material to realize actual visits to nature-based tourism destinations as well as factors that influence the stage of induced demand to not realize actual visit. Induced demand is demand stimulated by the provision of advanced facilities so that latent demand changes become actual demand (Jenkins & Pigram 2003).

MATERIALS & METHODS

The study was conducted by assessing printed and audio-visual material produced by the Ministry of Tourism from 2011-2016 in the form of booklets and tourism maps and VCDs containing films about nature-based tourism destinations. The printed material was divided into 24 booklets and seven (7) tourism maps and 16 audio visuals in the form of film VCDs about nature-based tourism destinations. Techniques for collecting data with literature studies and questionnaires. The populations in this study were 270 academic communities divided into three groups of respondents namely lecturers (as many as 30

respondents), ecotourism students (120 respondents) and communication students (120 respondents). Questionnaires that were distributed were closed ended type with purposive sampling. Data analysis using One Score One Indicator System and Kruskal Wallis test. Analysis of One Score One Indicator System is a scoring system with a scale that is used is 1-7, as a development of the 1-5 Likert Scale with the reason that the character of Indonesian society is very detailed in articulating a value (Avenzora 2008). The Kruskal Wallis and Dunn Further Test statistical analysis was used to prove the real differences (significance) that showed the response of attitudes and perceptions of the academic community.

Statistical Analysis

The study was carried out by distributing questionnaires in the form of close-ended patterns, namely by giving answers to respondents so they could choose the answers provided. The value or score used is a value of 1-7 (the result of the development of the 1-5 Likert scale) with the consideration that the people culturally have a tendency to give a longer range and almost never choose the lowest and highest answer (Avenzora 2008) . With a wider value scale, an assessment of various things from respondents will be closer to the actual value. Value or score 1 (highly not influential), 2 (not influential), 3 (slightly not influential), 4 (neutral), 5 (slightly influential), 6 (influential) and 7 (highly influential). The meaning pattern of each value can be adjusted to the needs.

The statistical test conducted in the study was the Kruskal Wallis Test and Dunn's Further Test. Kruskal Wallis to find out the significance of the polarization of direction and scale of attitudes which was then followed by the Dunn test if it was proven that there were significant differences between stakeholders. This non-parametric test is an alternative for the F test to test the similarity of some middle values in the analysis of variance if you want to avoid the assumption that the sample is

taken from a normal population (Walpole 1990). Junaidi (2015) explained that the Kruskal Wallis statistic is one of the non-parametric statistical equipment in the procedure group for independent samples. This procedure is used when wanting to compare two variables measured from unequal samples (free) and groups that are compared more than two. Kruskal-Wallis is a non-parametric alternative method, it can be used for ordinal or ranked data response data. The Kruskal Wallis Test formula can be written as equations:

$$H = \frac{12}{N(N+1)} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{R_i^2}{n_i} - 3(N+1)$$

Note : N = number of samples, Ri = number of ranks in group i, ni = number of samples in the group

The Kruskal Wallis Test results that showed significance were then followed up (posthoc tests) from ANOVA. The t-Dunnet advanced test was carried out after seeing a significant result or the hypothesis H0 was rejected. This test was also used to find out

between two groups of samples that were significantly different.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Attitudes and perceptions are an important part of psychographic assessment related to the decision making to visit to a nature-based tourism destination. This study will illustrate the factors that will influence visiting nature-based tourism destinations. The following are the results of the assessment of the attitudes and perceptions of the academic community at the stage of induced demand based on printed and audio-visual promotional materials regarding natural tourist destinations.

Attitudes towards Promotional Materials. The Kruskal Wallis Test results showed no significant differences between groups of respondents (P-value = 0.659 > α = 5%). Based on the assessment, all aspects of assessment can be interpreted as the choice of the respondent's attitude towards the promotion of nature-based tourism destinations.

Table 1. Respondents' Attitudes toward Promotional Materials

No.	Aspect of assessment	Lecturer	Ecotourism Students	Communication Students	Average
1.	Knowing the destination	5.8	5.9	5.9	5.8
2.	Giving an interest in nature-based tourism destinations	6.0	6.1	6.2	6.1
3.	Causing associative attitudes	6.1	5.9	6.1	6.1
4.	Making consideration into nature-based tourism destinations	6.2	5.9	6.1	6.1
5.	Recommending promotional material	6.0	6.0	5.9	6.0
6.	As guiding material towards or in nature-based tourism destinations	5.6	5.9	6.1	5.9
7.	Reading collection section	6.0	5.8	5.5	5.8

Keterangan: 1 = Very low; 2 = low; 3 = Slightly low; 4 = Medium; 5 = slightly high; 6 = High; and 7 = Very high.

Based on the assessment of respondents in the academic community, the highest average value of attitudes towards promotional material is first to generate interest in seeking more information about natural tourist destinations promoted Table 1. As stated by Howard & Sheth (1969) in Decrop (2000) promotional material as external input for prospective travelers to choose a destination. Regarding promotional material Belch & Belch (2003) also explained that tourism media users will evaluate printed material based on their ability to deliver as many messages as

possible to the audience. Efforts to do this, tourism media planners must consider the quality of publications, circulation and total readers and adjust to the audience to be achieved. Another attitude towards promotional material is creating a positive associative attitude towards the object being promoted, making material consideration towards the destination, recommending promotional material to relatives / family. Another attitude choice is to make promotional material as guiding material to and at the destination, knowing the destination and making promotional

material as part of the collection of reading or information. The results of the above assessment are meaningful promotional material for tourism, whether printed or audio visual nature does not cause differences in the attitudes of respondents in the academic community and shows the similarity of assessment among groups of respondents in the academic community regarding attitudes towards nature-based tourism promotion materials.

Opportunity to do Actual Visit. The Kruskal Wallis test results showed significant differences between audiences (P-value = 0.227 $\alpha = 25\%$). It can be interpreted that (1) There are differences in the perceptions of the academic community in aspects of assessment that influence the opportunity to do actual visits to promoted nature-based tourism destinations (2) Push factors and social demographic characteristics affect respondents so that different perceptions occur regarding opportunities do actual visits to promoted natural attractions.

Audience assessment with the highest average assesses aspects of time availability and financial ability as factors that influence the opportunity to do actual visit. This is in accordance with the statement of Little John & Baxter (2006) in the tourism market, various trips to be carried out have a different orientation including trips made between regions which are influenced by the level of financial dependence on the type of travel demand.

Differences in perceptions in assessing opportunities for actual visit were seen in the group of lecturer respondents with the student group of communication students (*Graphic 1*). Financial ability factors (score 6.5), physical (score 6.5) and time (score 6.6) are rated higher by the communication student respondent groups related to the opportunity to do actual visits, in addition other psychological factors become variables that also affect the student communication group respondents as needed, experience, knowledge and feelings. The influence of psychological variables in influencing tourist decisions is stated by Kotler (2005). These variables can be divided into motivation, perception, learning, beliefs and attitudes in this variable. This is also expressed by Sangadji & Sopiah (2013) that the five main psychological factors, namely motivation, perception, knowledge, beliefs and attitudes that will influence the choice of one's purchase. A person's behavior that arises from experience during his life is generated through encouragement, stimulation, cues, responses, and statements and it is included in the scope of learning. In the aspect of opportunities for actual visit, the respondent group of communication students rated the assessment aspect more highly, with lecture schedules and solid practicum, communication student respondents also needed tourism activities and to realize visits to natural attractions would consider economic factors such as financial and time, factors physical and psychological factors.

Note: 1 = highly not influential; 2 = Not influential; 3 = slightly not influential; 4 = neutral; 5 = slightly influential; 6 = influential; and 7 = highly influential

Graphic 1: Academic Community Perception of the Opportunity to Do Actual Visit

Note: 1 = highly not influential; 2 = Not influential; 3 = slightly not influential; 4 = neutral; 5 = slightly influential; 6 = influential; and 7 = highly influential

Graphic 2: Academic Community Perception of External Constraints for Not Realizing Actual Visit

Constraints for Not Realizing Actual Visit

In the context of making actual visits, there are obstacles not to make it happen. Constraints that arise can come from internal and external factors. The results of the assessment of respondents from the academic community regarding internal and external constraints not to realize the actual visit as follows.

Internal Factor Constraints. The Kruskal Wallis test showed no significant differences between audiences (P-value = 0.384 > $\alpha = 5\%$). This can be interpreted as all aspects of assessment affecting the audience's response as an internal obstacle not to realize actual visits to promoted natural attractions.

Table 2. Academic Community Perception Regarding Internal Factors

No	Aspect of assessment	Lecturer	Ecotourism Students	Communication Students	Average
1.	Financial limitations	6.0	6.1	6.2	6.1
2.	Physical limitations	5.6	5.6	5.7	5.7
3.	Time availability	6.0	6.1	6.0	6.0
4.	Personal understanding and trust	5.2	5.6	5.5	5.4
5.	Experience	5.6	5.7	5.5	5.6
6.	Lifestyle and personal taste	5.3	5.6	5.8	5.6
7.	Destination geographic factors	5.5	5.8	5.8	5.7

Note : 1 = highly not influential; 2 = Not influential; 3 = slightly not influential; 4 = neutral; 5 = slightly influential; 6 = influential; and 7 = highly influential

Based on Table 2, there are five aspects of influential assessment (score 6) and become an obstacle to internal factors not to realize actual visits to promoted nature-based tourism destinations. A rather influential assessment (score 5) was given by the lecturer respondent for aspects of personal understanding and trust and lifestyle and personal tastes. This personal factor is a consideration in choosing a tourist destination. This was conveyed by Um and Crompton (1991) in Decrop (2000) that travelers would consider internal inputs, namely the characteristics of social psychology in the form of personal

characteristics, motives, values and attitudes. The assessment aspect that gets the highest average score from personal constraints is the availability of time and financial limitations. Based on the results of these assessments, it can be interpreted that there is a similar view from the respondent group that internal factors and psychological factors have an effect as internal constraints not to realize actual visit.

External Factor Constraints. The Kruskal Wallis test conducted showed a very significant difference between audiences (P-value = 0.001 < $\alpha = 1\%$). Dunn's test results also show differences in

perceptions of the constraints of external factors not to actualize actual visits to communication student respondents with lecturer respondents who have a P-value of 0.002 less than the actual level used 0.01 ($\alpha = 1\%$). Conclusions reject H_0 , meaning that there are differences between communication student respondents and lecturers.

The difference in perceptions of external factor constraints does not only occur in the communication student respondents and lecturer respondents but also on the respondents of ecotourism students and lecturers. Significant results on the Kruskal Wallis test and Dunn test which showed a P-value of 0.012 less than the real level used 0.05 ($\alpha = 5\%$). Conclusions reject H_0 , meaning that there are differences in perceptions between groups of respondents on ecotourism and lecturers. Based on Graphic 2, there is a good difference in perceptions between the groups of ecotourism students and lecturers, besides that, between the communication student group and the lecturer respondent group, there will be external factors not to realize the actual visit. This indicates 1) There are differences in perceptions of external factors among the audience not to realize actual visits to promoted nature-based tourism destinations. (2) The results of the assessment show that the knowledge factors and aspects of the socio-demographic characteristics influence the understanding among audiences of external factors not to actualize visits to nature-based tourism destinations.

Differences in the assessment of external factor constraints between audiences not to actualize actual visit as stated by Durianto *et al* (2003) relate to understanding to interpret a stimulus derived from promotional material or other information obtained through the five senses. The meaning of stimulus will be different for each individual or group because it is influenced by three things. First is a stimulus category that involves classifying a stimulus by using concepts

stored in memory. Consumer behavior can be influenced by how to classify marketing stimuli. Promotion seeks to expand the attractiveness of the product by encouraging consumers to use several categories during the categorization process. Second is the elaboration of stimulus during stimulus processing. Elaboration refers to the amount of integration between new information and knowledge that has been stored in memory. Elaboration is along a continuum that ranges from low to high. The thoughts that arise when viewing promotional material can determine the persuasive impact of a stimulus. Third is a personal determinant in understanding. This third factor is influenced by stimulus and personal factors.

The difference in understanding of the external factor constraints on the student group respondents with the lecturer can be influenced by the understanding of the factors of knowledge, motivation and perceptions of the respondent groups regarding nature-based tourism destinations (Durianto *et al*, 2003). Knowledge stored in memory is the main determinant in understanding. Knowledge also increases the ability of consumers to understand a message. The lecturer respondent group was influenced by more mature age factors as much as 70% aged 26-45 years. This is influential in carrying out tourist activities in a destination that will consider a variety of high external risk factors. This is supported by research describing external factors that will affect tourism demand (Cooper & Hall (2007), Jedrysiak (2008) and Mason (2006)). Cooper & Hall (2008) explained that in general, travel security as one of the most important factors for traveling or not doing it. As a relevant example, namely the threat of terrorism (for example in the Middle East), political and social unrest (events in the North African region) and military conflicts have increased.

The results of many studies show that safety in a destination has special relevance for women and children. Jedrysiak (2008) also states that travel

choices can be determined by other risk factors such as the economic crisis, the bankruptcy of tourism companies, and others. Factors that are equally important are health risks (epidemics, infectious diseases, contaminated water, etc.). Other risk factors also determine travel choices including religious, social, cultural or the like. Mason (2006) more specifically illustrates the decline in maritime tourism demand due to external factors namely sea pollution and eutrophication that occurred in the Romagna Coast of Italy in 1989. Pollution originating from agriculture, urban and industrial waste stored in the Po River then flows into the Sea Adriatic. The incident caused a decrease in actual demand for tours at the destination. Based on the various studies above, it can be interpreted related to external constraints, demographic factors, namely the age of the respondent group and psychological factors from the aspect of understanding, causing the fragmentation of perceptions between lecturer respondent groups and student respondent groups not to realize actual visit.

CONCLUSION

Various influential factors related to the decision to make actual visits to nature-based tourism destinations. Influential factors are demographic factors, personal factors, external and psychological factors. Demographic factors such as age, education and work have an influence on the cognitive structure of the academic community. Internal factors related to physical abilities and time as well as social class and personality influences in realizing actual visits of promoted natural attractions. External factors that include risks from the situational environment that are in accordance with the respondent's typology will affect the image and perception of attractions and resources. Another external factor is promotional media which is a pre-activity stimulus. Promotional media in the form of print media and audio visual are factors that can affect both substance and design. The extent to which promotional

media exposure levels will also greatly affect respondents. Psychological factors are an important part that also influences respondents in deciding visits to promoted natural attractions such as perception, learning, beliefs and attitudes. In the context of psychological learning in the form of knowledge and experience causes social dynamics in individual behavior at the stage of induced demand.

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